

Utilization of fly ash for production of Al_2O_3 -cordierite composites

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Fly ash has been utilized for the preparation of alumina-cordierite composite. The required oxides were incorporated through semi colloidal route to enhance the reaction sintering process. The alumina-cordierite developed had superior thermo mechanical properties than pure cordierite.

There has been growing conciousness regarding safe disposal of different types of industrial waste and its utilization for some gainful purpose to solve environmental pollution. Fly ash is a by product obtained by burning pulverized coal in the thermal power plant during the production of electricity. Its mineralogical composition indicates that a large quantity of glassy matter is present alongwith some crystalline phases including mainly mullite and some amount of magnetite, hematite and α -quartz.

The mineral cordierite is of great importance in commercial field because of extremely low coefficient of thermal expansion and thermal shock resistance. Cordierite ceramics can be synthesized by various methods¹. For enhancing the reactivity of the ingredients, sol-gel process has also been used to generate cordierite phase by controlled crystallization from glassy phase².

The improved thermo mechanical properties of the cordierite ceramics composite containing anorthite and mullite phase respectively, has been incorporated to form composites³. The objective of the present investigation was to use an important industrial waste material such as fly ash for the preparation of cordierite, and for extending the firing range; excess alumina was added leading to alumina-cordierite composite. The required oxides were incorporated through semi colloidal route to enhance the reaction sintering process.

Batch mixture was composed in such a fashion that Batch-I contained pure cordierite composition and in other compositions Al_2O_3 content was gradually increased. The main ingredients were Bakreswar (India) fly ash $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ of 0.1 molar concentration. They were taken in a polythene container in which the calculated amount of fly ash was dispersed by thorough stirring. To

this homogeneous dispersion, 1 : 1 ammonia solution was slowly added with stirring until the pH was raised to 9. This was properly processed to remove the water-soluble impurities, dried at low temperature (45–50°C) and milled to fine state of subdivision. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of the sintered minerals was carried out using a Philips PW (1790) X-ray diffractometer where Ni filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation was used. The scanning electron microscope used for microstructural analysis was model S-530 Hitachi.

Present investigation was undertaken to compose cordierite-based bodies from the interaction of a waste material such as fly ash and Al_2O_3 and MgO .

Experimental

Molar ratio of Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 in the flyash was found to be 1 : 3.5, which indicates cordierite composition ($2\text{MgO} \cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{SiO}_2$) and MgO and more Al_2O_3 was to be incorporated in the system. The surface area of the Bakreswar fly ash (composition by percentage : SiO_2 , 62; Al_2O_3 , 30; CaO , 3.5; $\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$, 1.5; Fe_2O_3 , 2.5; LOI, 0.5; MgO , SO_4 trace) as selected for present work was $75 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which was sufficient enough for any powder processing work. From the XRD pattern of fly ash (Fig. 1) the crystalline phases were found to be mul-

Fig. 1. XRD of fly ash.

lite (major) along with quartz, haematite and magnetite as minor ones. The material also contains some siliceous glassy phase. The precursor powder containing different proportions of alumina in the cordierite composition was synthesized in the semi colloidal route by coating the fly ash particle with mixed hydroxides of aluminium and magnesium in the colloidal form. The purified precursor powder was finally milled. For fabrication purposes fine powder was calcined at 900°C and mixed with 10% uncalcined material, which acted as green bond. The pressed fabricated shapes were dried at 120°C and fired at different temperatures for a fixed soaking period of half an hour.

Results and discussion

For batches I-IV, compositions of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and MgO are 51.36, 34.93, 13.69; 48.45, 38.23, 13.00; 46.22, 41.44, 13.32; 41.89, 47.94, 10.95 respectively.

The first important fired property related to high temperature reaction i.e. linear shrinkage, which was associated with reaction sintering, liquid formation and subsequent recrystallization to generate newer phases. The shrinkage value of the pure cordierite was minimum and increased with increase in Al₂O₃ content. The shrinkage curves are parallel but not continuous in nature. Two inflections one at 1200°C and the other at 1250°C respectively beyond which shrinkage were not significant. With the progress of the reaction sintering process, the liquid formation led to the generation of some closed pores. Significant reduction of apparent porosity was observed at the two inflection points specially from 1150 to 1200°C. From the lower values of porosity it was evident that vitrification occurred at a faster rate, which follows an inverse relationship with alumina content. The mechanical properties of a polycrystalline material is very much dependent on the inherent bond nature and the formed microstructure. Maximum strength was achieved with the composition containing 20% alumina. From the nature of the curve (Fig. 2), the zone of strength development was found to be 1200 to 1250°C. The compositional effect played a vital role in the grain growth and interlocking. Rapid fluctuation of temperature usually generates stresses in a composite body depending on the microstructure and that is related to the phase transformation and the nature of the glassy phase at the grain

Fig. 2. Flexural strength-firing temperature relationship before thermal spalling of alumina-cordierite composites.

boundary. Temperature-residual flexural strength curves after eight thermal cycles at 800°C with 10 minutes duration in air quenching showed an inflection point at 1200°C up to which relative strength increased. But when compared with initial values, strength decreases from 1200 to 1250°C fired samples. Initially at lower temperature (1100°C) the flexural strength was found to increase after thermal spalling, which might be associated with secondary crystallization and proper interlocking. The relative high thermal shock resistance of this type of composite was related to proper cordierite formation and proper grain growth. In order to study the compositional effect on the generation of crystalline phases of the reaction sintered products X-ray diffraction analysis was performed with 1250°C fired samples as shown in Fig. 3. In each sample formation of cordierite phase was identified. In the alumina rich compositions, associated corundum phase was also observed. Complete interaction of fly ash was ascertained under this condition by the disappearance of lines of fly ash in the diffractogram.

The assessment of the phase assemblage in the microstructure was studied through scanning electron microscope and the micrographs of the 1250°C fired sample have been shown in Fig. 4. Compact microstructure with proper interlocking of cordierite grains was observed with gradual incorporation of alumina. The grain boundary became sharp probably because of diminution of glassy phase. Alumina was distributed in the round and the sub rounded morphology in the intergranular positions. Al₂O₃ did not have any significant influence on the grain growth of cordierite in the matrix.

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction of the samples fired at 1250°C.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrograph of sample fired at 1250°C (6000X).

Conclusion :

The alumino silicate type fly ash is a suitable material for preparing cordierite and cordierite-based composites at relatively low temperature. The zone of temperature for evolving suitable cordierite alumina composite was

1200–1250°C with this precursor powder obtained through semi colloidal route. Thermo mechanical properties of alumina cordierite were superior to pure cordierite.

References

1. C. C. Agrafiotis and A. Tsetsekou *J. Mat. Sci. Lett.*, 1999, **18**, 1421; Y. Hu and H-T. Tsai, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 2001, **36**, 123; A. G. Tomba Martinez and M. A. Camerucci, *Br. Ceram. Trans.*, 2002, **105**, 94; Y. M. Sung *et al.*, *Ceram. Int.*, 1997, **23**, 401; K. Sumi, Y. Kobayashi and E. J. Kato, *Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1999, **82**, 783.
2. S. Mei, J. Yang and J. M. F. Ferreira, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2001, **21**, 185; S. B. Sohn, S. Y. Choi and Y. K. Lee, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 2000, **35**, 4815; M. A. Villegas, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2002, **22**, 487; M. R. Boudchicha, S. Achour and A. Harabi, *J. Mat. Sci. Lett.*, 2001, **20**, 215; M. A. Camerucci, G. Urretavizcaya and A. L. Cavallieri, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2001, **21**, 1159.
3. S. Mei, J. Yang and J. M. F. Ferreira, *Mater. Lett.*, 2001, **47**, 205.